

Topic	Item	Checklist item description	Reported on Line
Title	1	The diagnosis or intervention of primary focus followed by the words “case report”	Title
Key Words	2	2 to 5 key words that identify diagnoses or interventions in this case report, including "case report"	Keywords
Abstract (no references)	3a	Introduction: What is unique about this case and what does it add to the scientific literature?	Abstract
	3b	Main symptoms and/or important clinical findings	Abstract
	3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutic interventions, and outcomes	Abstract
	3d	Conclusion—What is the main “take-away” lesson(s) from this case?	Abstract
Introduction	4	One or two paragraphs summarizing why this case is unique (may include references)	Introduction, Line 8
Patient Information	5a	De-identified patient specific information.	Case report, Line 1
	5b	Primary concerns and symptoms of the patient.	Case report, Line 2
	5c	Medical, family, and psycho-social history including relevant genetic information	Case report, Line 1
	5d	Relevant past interventions with outcomes	N/A
Clinical Findings	6	Describe significant physical examination (PE) and important clinical findings.	Case report, Line 3
Timeline	7	Historical and current information from this episode of care organized as a timeline	N/A
Diagnostic Assessment	8a	Diagnostic testing (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys).	Case report, Line 3-29
	8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access to testing, financial, or cultural)	N/A
	8c	Diagnosis (including other diagnoses considered)	Case report, Lines 14, 32
	8d	Prognosis (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	Case report, Line 32
Therapeutic Intervention	9a	Types of therapeutic intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	Case report, Line 34
	9b	Administration of therapeutic intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	N/A
	9c	Changes in therapeutic intervention (with rationale)	N/A
Follow-up and Outcomes	10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes (if available)	N/A
	10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	Case report, Line 34
	10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (How was this assessed?)	N/A
	10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	N/A
Discussion	11a	A scientific discussion of the strengths AND limitations associated with this case report	Discussion, Line 66
	11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature with references .	Discussion (all section)
	11c	The scientific rationale for any conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	Discussion (all section)
	11d	The primary “take-away” lessons of this case report (without references) in a one paragraph conclusion	Conclusion
Patient Perspective	12	The patient should share their perspective in one to two paragraphs on the treatment(s) they received	N/A
Informed Consent	13	Did the patient give informed consent? Please provide if requested	Yes ☒ No ☐